

CLIENT-SERVER ARCHITECTURE OF DISTRIBUTED DATABASE

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A client-server architecture involves the distribution of tasks and computing load among multiple computers connected to a network. The user's application program (the client part of the system) uses data by accessing the server, whose interface is based on the international standard of the Structured Query Language (SQL) query language.

Implementation of information systems in the "client-server" architecture has the following advantages, in particular, compared to the previous file-server architecture:

- reliability of information storage, resistance to hardware failures and wrong actions of employees that can lead to data loss;
- integrity of information, existence of built-in mechanisms that reduce the possibility of conflicts when entering and changing data;
- allocation of access to information for different categories of users (including remote users) according to their rights;
- minimization of network traffic due to reasonable load distribution between the server and the client, high performance;
- scalability, the ability to increase overall performance in proportion to the number of servers' processors and RAM. The implementation of the "client-server" architecture can be one-, two-, three-level or distributed depending on the tasks.

A three-tier architecture assumes the presence of a database server, a middleware server, and client workstations. A database server provides data storage and data sampling based on client requests. Middle layer functions include processing and transforming data sent to and from the server to the client according to defined logical rules. Client applications are installed on workstations and interact directly with the user. The number of client workstations depends on the workload, network bandwidth, and server capacity.

Figure 1. Client-server architecture

In a two-tier architecture, there is no intermediate layer and its functions are shared between the server and the client. On the one hand, this leads to an increase in speed and a decrease in network traffic. On the other hand, the cost of installing client applications in workplaces increases and the number of workstations that can be in the hundreds in an enterprise increases. In such circumstances, it is effective to simplify the client software as much as possible and install it on a computer with a weaker load. In the ideal case of using Internet technology, the server dynamically forms the results of the request in HTML format, and it is enough to have a browser installed at the client's workplace to view web pages.

Given the rapid development of computer technology, client computers can become powerful enough to load more database management functions on them, thereby reducing the server load for the entire system. At the same time, it is necessary to take into account the throughput of communication channels. From this point of view, a promising direction of database design is to provide flexible configuration and to distribute functions between client and server parts of MBBT during system installation. Implementation of the information system can also be done in a single-level architecture, only in this case the database is not distributed and is required.

Despite the advantages of the "client-server" architecture, file-server technology is also being used in the development of digital technologies. A centralized database can be successfully used as a file server to store large amounts of data used by many groups of users in an enterprise. This is due to the inefficiency of replicated databases as an alternative to distributed database technology. Synchronizing multiple copies of a database is a big challenge for administrators, who tend to keep backups in a single copy. If we take into account that the use of client-server technology leads to duplication of data, in order to solve this problem, it is necessary to choose the client-server architecture in the distributed database based on the organization's activities.

The choice of architecture depends on the specific goals of the information system development, the requirements for it, and the project budget. When starting to solve a practical problem, it is necessary to take into account the entire set of existing information technologies and choose the right concept based on the requirements of the automation object. The successful choice of technology depends on the level of understanding of the problem and its subject area.

The development of digital technologies, interactive services provided by state and economic management bodies and local government bodies, as well as non-governmental organizations and private sectors for individuals and legal entities, are all implemented on the basis of client-server architecture. As the number of organizations and interactive services increases, almost all services are moving to cloud computing platforms. In this case, the following questions arise.

1. An increase in the number of users sharply increases the number of requests sent to the servers of the database management system, as a result of which the response speed of the server decreases. How to maintain system response rate?
2. Due to the increase in the volume of data in the database, the informativeness of this database increases. How to ensure the security of the system in this case? That is, how to

solve the issue of ensuring the security of the database without reducing the productivity of users?

Figure 2. Client-server architecture is a cluster of servers

To solve these problems, it is possible to solve by distributing the database of corporate network users and placing information security components in the client-server architecture of the distributed database. This is done as follows.

First of all, it is necessary to introduce a server cluster because the increase in the number of users dramatically increases the number of requests sent to the servers of the database management system. The main reason for this is that the system will not stop if a server crashes when the number of requests increases. Another server will automatically perform this task. Server clustering protects against a denial of service situation when a server is overloaded with requests, but cannot maintain system performance.

Server Denial of Service situation when the number of requests increases because there is a cluster of servers, only because the system slows down, now the balancing servers are used to increase the speed of the system. When the number of users of the system is thousands and the number of requests sent by them exceeds several tens of millions, the speed of the system becomes very important. Because the longer the response time to which requests increases, the number of requests will increase dramatically. Because a new type of request comes into standby mode without receiving an answer to any request.

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